

(3H) and 4.48 δ (3H) for the eighteen protons of the six methoxyl groups. There was a triplet centered at 1.22 δ (3H, $J = 7$ Hz) for the methyl protons of the carboethoxyl group ($-\text{COOCH}_2\text{CH}_3$) and a quartet centered at 4.30 δ (2H, $J = 7$ Hz) for the methylene protons of the carboethoxyl group ($-\text{COOCH}_2\text{CH}_3$). The change in the chemical shift in the above spectrum was due to the solvent (Pyridine). As (Ic) was insoluble in CHCl_3 and CDCl_3 its NMR spectrum was carried out in pyridine.

Thus all the above data clearly indicated that the methylated product has the structure (Ia). In 1965 Schmidt⁵ *et al.* reported from *Quercus valonea* and *Q. macrolepis* the isolation of valoneic acid dilactone (Id) which formed a hexamethyl ether methyl ester (Ia). Although no direct comparison with authentic sample of hexamethyl ether of valoneic acid dilactone methyl ester has been possible there appears to be very little doubt that our methylated product is identical with hexamethyl ether of valoneic acid dilactone methyl ester. So it appears likely that the original polyhydroxy aromatic acid obtained from the leaves of *C. arborea* is valoneic acid dilactone although the possibility of the original acid being a partially methylated valoneic acid dilactone cannot be completely overruled.

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Mercuric Acetate as an Initiator of Vinyl Polymerization

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THE effects of metal salts on polymerization reactions are very diverse depending on the type of metal ion, the associated anion, the nature of monomer

and probably the medium in which the reaction is carried out. Spontaneous initiation of certain vinyl monomers by metal salts is reported by several workers¹⁻⁵.

Thus the examples of vinyl polymerization initiated by inorganic salts alone are not rare, but practically no evidence is available where mercuric acetate acts as an initiator of polymerization. While working on the effect of metal salts we observed that mercuric acetate can initiate polymerization of certain vinyl monomers. Attempts were made to study the kinetics of MMA-HgAc₂ system in DMF at 60° but unfortunately the results were not strictly reproducible. We however made some preliminary observations and tried to suggest a mechanism of polymerization. The observations included the study of the following: (1) monomer selectivity, (2) effect of solvent and (3) nature of reaction.

Monomer selectivity

Methylmethacrylate, styrene and acrylonitrile were successfully polymerized in DMF at 60° in the absence of oxygen using mercuric acetate (1×10^{-2} moles/lit) as an initiator; but in the case of acrylamide only initiation was observed under identical conditions.

Effect of solvent

Various solvents were used as the polymerization medium in the case of mercuric acetate initiated polymerization of methylmethacrylate at 60°. A measurable amount of polymer was obtained when the reaction was carried out in the solvents like DMF, formamide, *n*-butylamine and formic acid. But polymerization was not effected in solvents such as, acetonitrile, pyridine or alcohol. In all the cases the polymerization was homogeneous but in the case of formic acid blackish precipitation was found and this may be the precipitation of $\text{Hg}(\text{OOCH})_2$ or metallic mercury.

Nature of reaction

The polymerization of methylmethacrylate initiated by mercuric acetate in DMF at 60° was inhibited by both the diphenyl-picrylhydrazyl (DPPH) and *p*-benzoquinone. This suggests that probably free radical mechanism is operative in this case. This was further confirmed by co-polymer (MMA+styrene) analysis spectrophotometrically using the technique of Tobolsky *et al.*⁶ The principle of the method is that unlike polystyrene, poly-methylmethacrylate is optically clear above 250 nm in chloroform. So a copolymer of methylmethacrylate and styrene having different feed ratio was prepared at 60° in DMF using 1.13×10^{-3} mole/lit mercuric acetate as initiator. The polymer after rigorous purification by usual method was dried at 40° in an oven for 12 hr. Exactly 0.1% polymer solution in chloroform was made and optical density was measured using a Hilger Spectrophotometer at 269 nm. From the calibration curve⁶ percent of styrene in the copolymer at different

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NOTES

feed ratios was calculated and this result was compared with the result obtained from the reactivity ratio. The results are shown in the Table.

TABLE. SPECTROPHOTOMETRIC ANALYSIS OF COPOLYMER OF METHYLMETHACRYLATE AND STYRENE

Set	MMA in ml.	Styrene in ml	DMF in ml	Optical density O.D.	% of <i>p</i> -styrene from O.D.	% <i>p</i> -styrene from reactivity ratio
1	2.5	0.5	2.0	0.464	29.5	25.6
2	2.0	1.0	2.0	0.538	34.2	40.2
3	1.5	1.5	2.0	0.740	42.8	51.4
4	1.0	2.0	2.0	0.900	57.3	62.9

From the results it is clear that the composition is not exactly tallying with a conventional radical initiated copolymer, but is close to it. Moreover, the D.P. of polymethylmethacrylate prepared by

using mercuric acetate initiator is comparable to that of a sample of polymer obtained from a standard radical polymerization (say AIBN initiated) at identical rates of polymerization as achieved in mercuric acetate initiated systems. These added to the fact that polymerization is inhibited by conventional free radical inhibitors indicate the radical mechanism to be more probable.

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